

COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON NOVEL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Novel drug delivery systems (NDDS) provide several advantages, including greater bioavailability, stability, pharmacological activity, improved tissue distribution, protection against toxicity, prolonged delivery, and protection against physical and chemical degradation. Additionally, they offer benefits for delivery systems of herbal nanoparticle s, delivering the formulation directly to the site of action with improved pharm acokinetic effects, stability, and efficacy. With an emphasis on polymeric micelle s, liposomes, dendrites, and nanoparticles, recent advancements include phytosomes, liposomes, nanoparticles, emulsions, and microspheres. The “SL1ART” nanoparticle carrier technology provides tailored drug delivery to sick cells or tissues by enabling the release of medications in response to physiological events. Transport mechanism s for Nano-Carriers: Colloidal nanoparticles are

specifically delivered to particular cells or organs using both active and passive targeting techniques. Active targeting entails functionalising the surface of the nanoparticle with ligands to bind to particular receptors on targeted cells, whereas passive targeting depends on the increased permeability and retention effect. Numerous drug delivery systems, such as transdermal drug delivery systems like sonophore sis and osmotic pumps and carrier-ba sed systems like liposomes, nanoparticles, microspheres, niosomes, and re sealed erythrocytes, provide specialised methods for drug administration, enhancing therapeutic efficacy and patient outcomes. Pharmaceutical development prospects are increasing in India as a result of developments in excipient technology and novel drug delivery techniques, especially in the fields of molecular imprinting and smart nanoparticle-based drug delivery systems.

KEYWORDS: SART NANOCARRIER-BASED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS, LIPOSOMES, NANOPARTICLES. Solid lipid nanoparticles, Recent developments in novel drug delivery system of herbals, niosomes, SONOPHORESIS

INTRODUCTION

A herbal formulation is a dosage form that contains one or more herbs or processed herbs in predetermined amounts to offer particular nutritional, aesthetic, and/or other advantages. Herbal preparations are made by undergoing processes including distillation, extraction, expression, fractionation, purification, concentration, or fermentation on entire plants, broken or chopped plants, or plant fragments.^[1,2] The term “novel drug delivery system” (NDDS) refers primarily to the creation of novel pharmacological forms with enhanced properties such selective site targeting, higher permeability parameters, and smaller particle sizes. When compared to the effects of biotherapeutic drugs in conventional dose forms, NDDSs can be employed to improve their performance. This chapter will describe the idea of NDDS, the various design techniques, and some of their clinical.^[3]

Advantages of novel drug delivery system^[4]

1. Protection from physical and chemical degradation.
2. Sustained delivery.
3. improved tissue macrophages distribution.
4. Enhancement of pharmacological activity.
5. Protection from toxicity.
6. Increased bioavailability.
7. Enhancement of solubility^[5]
8. Enhancement of stability.

Advantages of herbal nanoparticle delivery system

1. Nanoparticulate system delivers the herbal formulation directly to the site of action.
2. Increased efficacy and therapeutic index.
3. Increased stability via encapsulation.
4. Improved pharmacokinetic effect.
5. Producing with various sizes, compound surface properties.^[4,6]

Recent developments in novel drug delivery system of herbals:

1. Phytosome
2. Liposome
3. Nanoparticles
4. Emulsions
5. Microsphere
6. Ethosome
7. Solid lipid nanoparticle
8. Niosome G
9. Proniosome s
10. Transdermal Drug Delivery System
11. Dendrimers
12. Liquid Crystals
13. Hydrogels^[4,7]

The pharmaceutical drug delivery system typically comprises:

1. a suitable dose form (pharmaceutical formulations) that administers the drug into the body.
2. The release mechanism of a drug from the dosage form to the target cells of targeting after administration.
3. An optimum medical device/pharmaceutical technique used for manufacturing the dosage form.

Therefore a NDDS could be obtained:

1. Formulation of SMART Nano carrier-based drug delivery systems to improve the cell selective for enhanced targeting.
2. Superior controlling of the duration of action (SMART extended release drug delivery systems).
3. Utilization of novel techniques of manufacturing, for example, microfluidics (MF).

SMART NANOCARRIER-BASED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS

A carrier-based drug delivery method indicates that drug molecules will be encapsulated within vehicular and/or polymeric systems. Some examples of SMART Nano systems are polymeric micelles, liposomes, dendrites, and nanoparticles (NPs).^[1] The design of a Nano system with optimum characteristics such as higher drug-loading capacity, smaller particle

size (5300 nm), and controllable release profile are the main goals for designing a successful pharmaceutical product. The term “SMART” means that the Nano carrier drug delivery system can release the drug in response to physiological stimuli thereby targeting it to the diseased cells/tissue with an extended/controllable manner.^[3,8,9]

Fig. 1.4: Smart drug delivery system.

Mechanisms of nano-carrier transport within systemic circulation to specific targets.

PASSIVE TARGETING: Passive targeting is the primary pathway for a colloidal Nano system via the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect.^[3,10]

ACTIVE TARGETING: Active targeting is an advanced strategy used to ensure selectivity and specificity of SMART Nano system to the targeted site/organs/cells. The primary technique to mitigate the impact of anticancer medicines on healthy tissues is their targeted delivery to malignant tissue. The technique of active targeting should be considered during preparation of the SMART noncolloidal system via functionalization of the surface of the carrier with ligands, which specially bind with its corresponding receptor on the surface of the targeted cell. Ligand—receptor attachment can guarantee that the Nano system will be optimally delivered to the diseased cells rather than the surrounding healthy tissue. Alternative drug delivery methods aim to identify viable routes for administering protein drugs beyond the gastrointestinal tract, where degradation may occur, or to overcome specific delivery barriers, such as the blood-brain barrier (BBB), to enhance drug targeting and efficacy.^[3,12,13]

Various Drug Delivery Systems:

Carrier based Drug Delivery System:

- 1) Liposomes
- 2) Nanoparticles
- 3) Microspheres
- 4) Niosomes
- 5) Res0aluçt erythrocyte s a s drug carriers

Transdermal Drug Delivery Systems:

- i. Sonophoresis
- ii. Osmotic pump
- iii. Microencapsulation

A) LIPOSOMES

Liposomes are drug-encapsulating, self-assembling vesicles composed of phospholipids that enclose a central aqueous compartment, forming either many concentric bilayers (multilamellar) or a single bilayer (unilamellar). The phospholipid bilayer of liposomes is 4-5 nm thick, and their sizes range from 30 nm to the micrometre scale. British scientist Alec Bangham and associates at Babraham Cambridge established the science of liposomology in the middle of the 1960s, publishing the structure of liposomes for the first time in 1964.^[1,13,14]

Structure

Fig. 1.2: Recent advancement in liposome technology.

Fig. 1.3: Wpas of liposomas.

Manufacturing of liposomes

Liposomes can be prepared by many methodologies. The process of liposome manufacture and the phospholipids type critically affects the final liposomes characteristics²⁰. Liposome's fabrication procedures can be classified into^[1,15]

1. The Bangham method of thin-film hydration

2. Reverse phase evaporation technique - I

a. Liposomes preparation via thin -film hydration extrusion technique.^[16]**Advantages of Liposomes**

1. Liposomes can be delivered either systemically or non-systemically and are characterised by their non-toxicity, biocompatibility, biodegradability, and non-immunogenicity.
2. Actinomycin's therapeutic index and effectiveness can be raised by encapsulating it in liposomes.
3. The ability of liposomes to connect with ligands unique to particular sites allows for active targeting.
4. Anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer medications that target particular sites.
5. Has a high tissue penetration rate (insulin, corticosteroids, and anesthetics).

B. NANOPARTICLES

A particle of matter with a dimension ranging from one to one hundred nanometres (nm) is designated as a nanoparticle or ultrafine particle. Nanoparticles are typically distinguished from microparticles (1-1000 μm), "fine particles" (sized between 100 and 2500 nm), and "coarse particles" (ranging from 2500 to 10,000 nm) or electrical characteristics.

Nanoparticles (including nanospheres and nanocapsules of size 10-200 nm) are in the solid state and are either amorphous or crystalline. They can encapsulate and/or adsorb a medication, shielding it from enzymatic and chemical breakdown. Because of their uses in

controlled drug release, targeted delivery to particular organs or tissues, DNA transport in gene therapy, and the ability to deliver proteins, peptides, and genes orally, biodegradable polymeric nanoparticles have attracted a lot of attention recently as possible drug delivery systems.^[17,18,19]

Advantages of nanoparticles^[20]

The subsequent advantages of employing nanoparticles as a drug delivery technology are as follows:

- 1) After parenteral injection, it is simple to modify the size and surface properties of nanoparticles to accomplish both passive and active medication targeting.
- 2) They manage and maintain the drug's release throughout transportation and at the location of localization, modifying the drug's distribution throughout the body and its eventual elimination to enhance therapeutic efficacy and minimize negative effects.
- 3) Targeting particular sites can be accomplished by the use of magnetic guiding or by affixing targeting ligands to particle surfaces.
- 4) The system may be administered through a variety of methods, including as intraocular, parenteral, nasal, and oral.

Types of Nanoparticles^[21]

1. Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs)
2. Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLC)
3. Fullerenes
4. Nanoshells
5. Quantum dots (QD)
6. Super paramagnetic nanoparticles

1) Solid lipid nanoparticles

Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) represent an innovative medicinal delivery mechanism or formulation. Conventional methods for delivering medications to intestinal lymphatics include the use of permeation enhancers, surface modification, prodrug synthesis, complex formation, and colloidal lipid carrier-based tactics. Moreover, liposomes, microemulsions, micellar solutions, polymeric nanoparticles, self-emulsifying delivery methods, and most recently, solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN) have been created to deliver medications to intestinal lymphatics.

Furthermore, a number of potential vehicles for oral intestinal lymphatic delivery have been investigated, including polymeric nanoparticles, self-emulsifying delivery systems, liposomes, microemulsions, micellar solutions, and most recently, solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN). The normal shape of a solid lipid nanoparticle is spherical, with an average diameter of 10-1000 nanometres. Lipophilic compounds can be dissolved by the solid lipid core matrix found in solid lipid nanoparticles. The emulsifiers, or surfactants, stabilise the lipid core. Triglycerides (like tristearin), diglycerides (like glycerol behenate), monoglycerides (like glycerol monostearate), fatty acids (like stearic acid), steroids (like cholesterol), and waxes (like cetyl palmitate) are all included in the broad definition of "lipid" used here. To stabilise the lipid dispersion, emulsifiers of all classes (in terms of charge and molecular weight) have been employed.

It has been found that the combination of emulsifiers might prevent particle agglomeration more efficiently. The essential components of solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs), which have mean diameters ranging from 50 nm to 1000 nm for colloidal drug delivery applications, are lipids that stay solid at normal temperature and surfactants for emulsification.

SLNs offer unique properties such as small size, large surface area, high drug loading, the interaction of phases at the interfaces, and are attractive for their potential to improve performance of pharmaceuticals, nutraceuticals and other materials. Spray drying, high.

3) Fullerene

Any molecule made completely of carbon that takes the shape of a hollow tube, ellipsoid, or sphere is called a fullerene. Buck balls are another name for spherical fullerenes, where as buck tubes or carbon nanotubes are the names for cylindrical ones. In addition to sharing structural similarities with graphite, which is made up of stacked grapheme sheets of connected hexagonal rings, fullerenes can also have pentagonal (or occasionally heptagonal) rings, which could result in potentially porous molecules.^[21]

4) Nanoshells

Another name for nanoshells is core-shells. Nanoshells are spherical cores of a certain substance (concentric particles) encased in a thin layer of another material that is between 1 and 20 nm thick. Compared to their single component counterparts or nanoparticles of the same size, highly functional materials known as nanoshell particles exhibit altered and enhanced capabilities.^[21]

5) Quantum Dots (QD)

Semiconductor nanocrystals and core-shell nanocrystals with interfaces between various semiconductor materials make up quantum dots. Quantum dots' diameter typically rises to 5–20 nm following polymer encapsulation, although their size can be continually adjusted between 2 and 10 nm. Renal filtration rapidly removes particles smaller than 5 nm.^[21]

6) Super paramagnetic nanoparticles

Molecules that are drawn to a magnetic field but lose their magnetism when the field is removed are said to be super paramagnetic. Iron oxide nanoparticles with sizes between 5 and 100 nm have been applied to selective magnetic bio-separations. Typical methods for separating the particles from the surrounding matrix include covering them with antibodies to cell-specific antigens.^[21,22]

Method of Preparation

1. Solvent evaporation method
2. Spontaneous emulsification method
3. Salting out/emulsion diffusion method

A. MICROSPHERES

The microspheres are also known as micro-particles. They are designed to solve some of the problems with conventional therapy and increase a drug's therapeutic efficacy. To accomplish the desired outcome.^[1]

METHOD OF PREPERATION

- Emulsion Solvent Evaporation Technique.

Classification

- **Microsphere**

Typically, microspheres are free-flowing powders made of synthetic polymers or proteins that are biodegradable and preferably have a particle size of less than 200 µm. Polymers are the materials used to manufacture microspheres.

They are classified into two types

1. Synthetic Polymers.
2. Natural polymers.

Synthetic polymers are divided into two types

A) Non-biodegradable Polymers

- Poly methyl methacrylate (P 1 1A)
- Glycerylmethacrylata
- Epoxy Polymers.

B) Biodegradable polymers.

- LaCtides, Glycoside's& their co polymers
- Poly alkyl cyano acrylates
- Poly anhydride s

B. NIOSOMES

A new vehicular drug delivery technology called niosomes can be utilized to administer medications in a prolonged, regulated, and targeted way. Since niosomes are made of non-ionic surfactants, they are not harmful.

Advantages of niosomes

1. Niosomal dispersion in an aqueous phase can be emulsified in a non - aqueous phase to regulate the pace of drug delivery and produce a normal vesicle in an external non - aqueous medium.
2. They are both osmotically active and stable, which increases the stability of the entrapped medicine.
3. They improve the oral bioavailability of drugs that are poorly absorbed as well as the epidermal penetration of pharmaceuticals.
4. To get to the site of action, they can be applied top ically, administered parenterally, or taken orally, Because the surfactants are nonimmunogenic, biodegradable, and biocompatible, they can be used safely in the niosome synthesis process.

METHOD OF PREPARATION^[1]

- 1) Reverse-phase evaporation method
- 2) Transdermal Drug Delivery Systems

A) SONOPHORESIS

This technique greatly speeds up the absorption of topical medications (transdermal administration) into the dermis, epidermis, and appendages of the skin by using ultrasonic radiation. Sonophoresis is a rapid, simple, non-invasive, focused method of delivering macromolecules and low molecular weight drugs to the skin. By modifying skin tissue through a combination of chemical, mechanical, and temperature changes, sonophoresis is believed to enhance drug delivery mechanistically. Ultrasound at various frequencies between 20 kHz and 16 MHz, with intensities up to 3W/cm, has been used to accomplish sonophoresis.^[1,23,24,25,27,26,28]

MECHANISMS OF ACTION

Even though sonophoresis has drawn a lot of attention lately, little is known about how it works. Acknowledged, admitting that exposure to ultrasonography may result in a number of events.

These consist of

- Cavitation (generation and oscillation of gas bubbles).
- Thermal effects (temperature increase).
- Induction of convective transport.

C) Osmotic Pump

Most osmotic delivery systems, commonly referred to as osmotic pumps, consist of osmogen and a drug-filled core. With one or more drug delivery pores and a semi-permeable membrane covering them, the drug can be progressively administered as a suspension or solution.^[29] More advancements in implanted pumps occurred in the 1970s, although their application was restricted to animals. Osmosis served as the basis for this innovative approach, and the new pumps may be smaller than traditional constant-rate pumps. In the seventies and eighties.^[30]

D) MICROENCAPSULATION

Solids, liquids, or even gases can be encased in microscopic particles by creating thin wall material coatings around them using the microencapsulation technique.

ADMINISTRATI ON ROUTES

Patient acceptability, the drug's characteristics (such as solubility), accessibility to a disease site, or efficacy in treating a particular disease all influence the delivery method selection. The peroral route is the most significant medication delivery method. Drugs based on proteins and peptides are becoming more and more common. Although they have the most promise for more potent treatments, they are difficult to penetrate biological membranes and mucosal surfaces, are readily denatured or broken down, are prone to quick clearance in the liver and other body tissues, and need to be dosed precisely. Protein medications are currently typically given via injection, but this method is less comfortable and has issues with fluctuating blood drug levels. Therefore, the peroral route is still the most thoroughly researched because it offers benefits like ease and affordability of administration, as well as potential manufacturing cost savings, despite the obstacles to successful drug delivery that exist in the gastrointestinal tract (i.e., acid-induced hydrolysis in the stomach, enzymatic degradation throughout the gastrointestinal tract by several proteolytic enzymes, and bacterial fermentation in the colon.^[31]

Future Prospects and Opportunities in India

One of the most important areas for the pharmaceutical industry is India. As a result, numerous global behemoths have expressed a strong desire to invest and expand in this industry. The use and development of a wide range of excipients will be greatly impacted by advancements in the new and sophisticated NDDS procedures. India is renowned for being able to quickly adopt novel excipients and related technology. Therefore, the Indian excipient market will expand in two ways: first, by exporting novel organic excipients, and second, by using new excipients in a variety of cutting-edge delivery systems. The vast majority of the nation's pharmaceutical firms have been submitting and being granted new patents in the area of innovative drug delivery methods.^[32,33]

Molecular imprinting technology

There is a lot of promise for producing acceptable therapeutic dosage forms using the molecular imprinting method. In molecular imprinting, the template molecule and functional monomers or functional oligomers (or polymers) with particular chemical structures that are intended to interact with the template through covalent, noncovalent (self-assembly), or both forms a prepolymerization complex. 3. The main goal of current research is to target medicine delivery. Following the invention of the magic bullet, only a small number of

focused formulations were able to make it to market. The practical important difficulties of focussing on biomolecules are frequently brought to the forefront by the discoveries in the fields of molecular biology, biotechnology, and pharm acogenomics. For example, tailored medicine or gene delivery for tumours is one of the m ost sought-after therapeutic needs of the future.

CONCLUSION

The chapter concludes by outlining many innovative drug delivery systems (NDDS) and highlighting their noteworthy benefits as well as current advancements in formulations for herbal and nanoparticle drugs. By offering protection against degradation, sustained release, enhanced bioavailability, and targeted action, NDDS increase medication delivery. This is especially helpful in efficiently treating illnesses while reducing adverse effects.

Numerous sophisticated systems have been created, such as liposomes, phytosomes, nanoparticles, and niosomes. Each of these systems has special qualities like enhanced stability, tailored delivery methods, and better therapeutic indices. Osmotic pumps and sonophoresis are two other examples of cutting-edge methods to improve macromolecule delivery and preserve medication release patterns. Developments in NDDS and molecular imprinting technology are anticipated to transform drug delivery systems and tackle current therapeutic issues as India keeps investing in the pharmaceutical industry. This points to a bright future for modern medicine's use of focused, effective, and customised therapies.

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